

Solvent selection in extraction of bioactive and therapeutic components from Indian fresh water mussel *Lamellidens marginalis*

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Abstract : Extraction of therapeutic components from any biomass feedstock is primarily dependent on the solvent. There exists a variety of organic solvents and their combinations, which are commonly used in food and pharmaceutical industries. Out of this wide spectrum, three most commonly used mixed-solvents of chloroform-methanol, hexane-isopropanol and ethanol-diethyl ether were chosen to extract the therapeutic components from the edible part of Indian fresh water mussel *Lamellidens marginalis*. In addition to the standard physico-chemical characterizations of the extracts, an objective function was formulated to sort out the most potent solvent system. Instead of only accounting the standard rating parameters, therapeutic potentials, like anti-oxidant and anti-inflammatory properties of the extracts were quantified and incorporated in the objective function along with the yield, solvent cost and pertinent hazard potentials. The proposed method can be directly used to choose the most appropriate solvent in extraction of valuable components from any complex biomass feedstock.

Keywords : Solvent optimization, fresh water mussel, therapeutic potential, objective function, optimization parameters.

Introduction

The concept of functional food and their significance in human health has immensely changed the idea of diet¹. As they provide “health benefit beyond basic nutrition”, functional foods from the edible extracts of different naturally occurring bioactive materials of both plant and animal origin are on a high rise in recent times². Mussels, a species of class *Bivalvia mollusca* is one such extensively investigated species having a wide range of therapeutic implications. These are either marine or fresh water in nature, with majority of research work, reported so far, been conducted on marine species. Over the decades, mussels have been extensively studied for their potential as an

anti-inflammatory, anti-arthritic and antioxidant agent³. For example, Lyprinol, a patented extract of NZ marine mussel, *Perna canaliculus*, produced by supercritical carbon dioxide extraction method, has been reported to be effective in treatment of osteoarthritis, rheumatoid arthritis, bronchial tightness and even hypersensitivity⁴⁻⁶. Lyprinol, which primarily consists of sterol esters, triglycerides, free fatty acids, sterol and phospholipids, is abundant in n-3 PUFA (particularly in EPA and DHA) and the complex mixture of long chain PUFA has been reported to enhance its anti-arthritic activity⁷. Compared to the standard non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs); like aspirin, indomethacins etc., Lyprinol was found to be devoid of gastrointestinal side effects⁸. More-

over, in antigen-induced polyarthritis and collagen (II)-induced autoallergic arthritis in Dark Agouti rats, the ED₅₀ value of Lyprinol (≤ 15 mg kg⁻¹) was observed to be lower than that of naproxen (≥ 25 mg kg⁻¹), a non-steroidal, non-selective cyclooxygenase (COX) inhibitor⁴. Different mussel extracts, other than Lyprinol, were also reported to block the cyclooxygenase and lipoxygenase mediated oxygenation of arachidonic acid (AA) to different prostanoids, which are mediators of inflammatory and anaphylactic reactions^{6,9,10}.

Besides its vast anti-inflammatory responses, mussel extracts also exert several other therapeutic functions. It is interesting to note that different mussel oil extracts have resulted in significant effectiveness during clinical trials on children suffering from attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD)¹¹. Different peptide fractions of mussel extract, other than the bioactive lipids, also exhibit strong antimicrobial¹², antioxidant^{13,14}, anti-hypertensive¹⁵ and anti-coagulant¹⁶ properties.

Though fewer in number, but some significant reports are also available on the therapeutic properties of fresh water mussels. Extract of Indian fresh water species, *Lamellidens marginalis* (LM) was demonstrated to stabilize lysosome and protect the cartilage by releasing anti-inflammatory cytokines in case of adjuvant induced arthritis in male albino rats¹⁰. In another study, polysaccharides isolated from Chinese fresh water mussel *Hyriopsis cumingii* (HCPS) was reported to exhibit remarkable antioxidant activity in D-galactose induced, aged mice model¹⁷. The water soluble HCPS was also reported to function as a potential immunomodulator in 2,4-dinitrofluorobenzene induced delayed type hypersensitivity (DTH) reactions¹⁸.

In addition to explore the broad spectrum therapeutic potential of extracts obtained from different natural resources, selection of the optimum solvent that maximizes the product yield and pertinent bioactivities at the cost of minimum operating expense and environmental hazards is technically important. Primarily, the performance of a solvent should be judged

in terms of its partitioning ability of lipid and non-lipid components (sugar, peptides, amino acids etc.) between the solvent phase and the feedstock. However, therapeutic performance is often independent of the respective yield and may not even be dependent on a specific constituent. In several cases, reports are available that illustrate higher bioactivity of the gross extract than the purified peptide/lipids responsible for the specific function¹⁹. Traditionally, mixed organic solvents like chloroform-methanol²⁰, ethanol-diethyl ether²¹, hexane-isopropanol²² etc. are widely used to extract bioactive compounds from a broad range of samples. Supercritical fluid extraction (SFE) technology, on the other hand, may be regarded as environmentally beneficial alternative to the conventional organic solvent-based techniques. At the same time, SFE is prone to high capital investment because of abnormally elevated pressure condition (minimum 60 bar)²³. Therefore, organic solvent-based extraction processes are still more popular in the context of bioactive constituent extraction from natural feedstock²⁴.

The present work has been undertaken in an attempt to optimize the solvent system to be used in extraction of bioactive and therapeutic components from the Indian fresh water mussel *Lamellidens marginalis* (LM). In addition to the standard physico-chemical characterization of extracts obtained from different solvent systems, the optimization was carried out with a system-specific global objective function. The objective function was formulated based on the following parameters : (i) overall yield, (ii) total antioxidant status, (iii) nitric oxide release in lipopolysaccharide (LPS) induced macrophage activation model, (iv) cost of solvents and (v) overall hazard scores of solvents according to the different environmental standards.

Experimental

Chemicals and reagents :

RPMI 1640, phosphate buffered saline (pH 7.2), penicillin, streptomycin, gentamycin, amphotericin were purchased from Himedia Laboratories Pvt. Ltd.,

India. LPS was procured from Sigma Aldrich, India. Petroleum benzene, n-hexane, diethyl ether, chloroform, isopropanol, methanol, dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) were purchased from SRL, Mumbai, India. Absolute alcohol and sodium sulphate were procured from Bengal Chemical, India and SRL, India respectively. For biochemical assessments of cholesterol and triglycerides, commercial kits from Span Diagnostics Ltd., India was used.

Animals :

Swiss male albino mice (20 ± 5 g) were procured from the animal facility at M/s Chakraborty Enterprise (CPCSEA, Regd. No. 1443/PO/11/CPCSEA, Kolkata, India). They were housed in contamination free cages under controlled environmental conditions (temperature : 24 ± 2 °C, relative humidity : 64 ± 5 %, 12 h day/night cycle) with balanced diet and filtered water *ad libitum*. All experiments were performed according to the respective guideline for control and supervision of experiments on animal, Government of India.

Sample collection and extraction of constituents :

Adult fresh water mussel, *Lamellidens marginalis* (LM), was collected from local market of Kolkata, India. The edible part was isolated, homogenized and subjected to solvent extraction according to the standard protocols using different mixed organic solvents. Three samples, each of 500 g LM biomass homogenate were subjected to solvent extraction using three different mixed organic solvents of (i) chloroform-methanol (CM), (ii) hexane-isopropanol (HI) and (iii) ethanol-diethyl ether (EDE) following standard protocols²⁰⁻²². The residual solvents were separated from the extract phases by vacuum evaporation at 35 °C. The yield of dried extract was measured and stored at -10 °C after nitrogen purging for further use. The dried extracts with CM, HI and EDE have been coded as LME-1, LME-2 and LME-3 respectively.

Moisture content and drying curve of LM :

The equilibrium moisture and the drying curve of LM (edible portion only) were determined in a standard batch dryer (KCMT-142, K. C. Engineers (P.)

Ltd., Ambala, India) under constant drying condition with bone-dried air at 110 °C (air velocity : 1.83 m s^{-1}).

Physico-chemical properties of extracts :

Different physico-chemical properties of the three extracts, namely LME-1, LME-2 and LME-3 were investigated, which includes (i) relative density, (ii) refractive index, (iii) acid value, (iv) saponification index, (v) iodine value, (vi) triglycerides and cholesterol, (vii) total carotene content, (viii) UV-Vis spectra, (ix) IR spectra and (x) fatty acid composition by gas chromatography. The investigations were also repeated with olive oil for the sake of comparison.

Relative densities were measured by a picnometer using 1 ml of each sample.

For refractive index measurement, each sample was dissolved in ethanol to get a standardized concentration of 0.01 g L^{-1} and subsequently the refractive index was measured using an ERMA refractometer⁸.

Acid values of $\{\text{LME-}i\}_{i=1,3}$ and olive oil, which indicate the rancidity of the samples, were measured by first solubilizing the samples in absolute ethanol followed by titration against 0.1 N KOH with phenolphthalein indicator.

Saponification index is a measure of the average molecular weight of the fatty acid content present in a lipid sample. For this analysis, each sample was dissolved in KOH (2 g in 25 ml) and was titrated against 0.5 N HCl.

For iodine value measurement, 0.25 g of sample was dissolved in 10 ml of chloroform, which was followed by the dissolving this in 30 ml of Wijs solution (iodine monochloride in acetic acid). After keeping the solution in dark for 1 h, 10 ml of 15% KI solution was added and continuously shaken. Subsequently, 100 ml of distilled water was mixed. The resultant solution was then titrated against 0.1 N $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ in presence of 1 ml starch solution until the color (blue) of the present solution disappeared.

Cholesterol content of the extracts and the olive oil were measured by the standard technique outlined

by Zlatkis *et al.*²⁵, using a commercially available biochemical kit (CHOD-PAP, Span Diagnostic Ltd., India). Similarly, triglyceride present in the samples was estimated by using another biochemical kit (GPO-PAP, Span Diagnostic Ltd., India) following the single run enzymatic procedure outlined by Sullivan *et al.*²⁶.

According to the method proposed by Simpson and Haard²⁷, equal quantities of accurately weighted samples were dissolved in 10 ml of spectroscopic grade petroleum ether (40–60 °C) for total carotene content measurement. The respective absorbance values were recorded at 468 nm using an UV-Vis-IR spectrophotometer (UV-4100, Hitachi).

Spectrophotometric analysis of each sample was performed upon dissolving a few drops of the sample in n-hexane (1 : 2 v/v). Once again, the experiments were performed with the same spectrophotometer as used in carotene analysis.

FTIR spectra of all the extracts along with olive oil were recorded using a Nicolet-iS5 instrument (ASB 1401182, Thermo Scientific), equipped with an ATR/iD3 accessory. The samples were dissolved in n-hexane (1 : 2 v/v) and each spectral profile was recorded over the range of 3500–500 cm^{-1} .

Fatty acid compositions of the samples were evaluated by a gas chromatograph (6890n, Agilent). The instrument was fitted with a DB-wax capillary column (ID : 0.25 m, length : 30 m) and a FID detector. N_2 , H_2 and airflow rates were maintained 1, 30 and 300 ml min^{-1} respectively. Prior to injection, lipid constituents of the sample were derivatized to their respective methyl-esters using 7% BF_3 -methanol method²⁸. Dry hexane solution of methyl-esters was then injected directly into the gas chromatograph. Inlet and detector were maintained at 250 °C. The oven temperature was controlled as 150°–190°–230 °C with a rate of 15 °C min^{-1} initially, followed by a reduced rate of 4 °C min^{-1} in the second stage. The percent wise compositions of all the samples were corrected with respect to the authentic standards.

Toxicity study :

An *in vitro* study was carried out on murine perito-

neal macrophages, using lipid dose in the range of 6–12 $\mu\text{gm ml}^{-1}$ (with a regular interval of 2 $\mu\text{gm ml}^{-1}$) for all the three extracts. This study was adopted to determine a non-toxic dose for further *in vitro* studies. Peritoneal macrophages were treated with all the extracts dissolved in 0.2% DMSO (v/v) and incubated overnight in complete RPMI 1640 medium in a CO_2 incubator. The viability of the cells were assessed on the next day by trypan blue assay using a hemocytometer (Pneubach hemocytometer) under the microscope.

Bioactivity and therapeutic potential analysis :

Measurement of total antioxidant status (TAS) :

TAS values of the three different extracts were measured in terms of $\text{ABTS}^{\bullet+}$ radical cation scavenging activity according to the protocol reported by Re *et al.*²⁹. However, the final TAS values were reported in mM Trolox equivalent scale. 10 μL of each extract, with different dilution (10–100 mg ml^{-1}) were solubilized in 1 ml of standard $\text{ABTS}^{\bullet+}$ solution. After incubation for 6 min at room temperature, in dark, the absorbance was recorded at 734 nm. For each sample, percentage reduction of $\text{ABTS}^{\bullet+}$ was evaluated and compared with that of trolox. Subsequently, the TAS profiles over the mentioned concentration range of three different extracts were generated. For the purpose of solvent optimization, the TAS values, at an extract concentration of 50 mg ml^{-1} were selected to represent the antioxidant property of the extracts.

Anti-inflammatory activity in LPS-induced macrophage activation model :

The anti-inflammatory properties of LME-1, 2 and 3 were evaluated by conducting experiments on *in vitro* primary macrophage culture. Peritoneal macrophages were isolated from Swiss albino mice upon injecting sterile chilled PBS (0.1 M, pH 7.4). Red blood cells, present in the suspension were lysed by adding 0.8% NH_4Cl solution. After washing thrice, cell pellets were gently re-suspended at 1×10^6 cells ml^{-1} in complete RPMI 1640 medium with 2 mM L^{-1} glutamine, supplemented with 10% FBS, 10 U ml^{-1}

penicillin and 100 µg ml⁻¹ streptomycin. After seeding at 1 ml per sterile cover slip, cells were cultured overnight for adherence at 37 °C in a humidified atmosphere with 5% CO₂. The following day, the cells were incubated with LME-1, 2 and 3 (10 µgm ml⁻¹) dissolved in 0.2% DMSO (v/v) for 6 h, followed by LPS stimulation for another 18 h. A normal control and a vehicle control (DMSO) were also maintained for comparison. After incubation, the culture supernatant was collected, centrifuged and analyzed for NO concentration by spectrophotometric assay (550 nm) using Greiss reagent³⁰. For exact measurement of NO concentration levels, NaNO₂ standard curve (2–40 µg) was used.

Hazard ratings of solvents :

Apart from extract yield and selectivity with respect to different bioactive lipid and/or proteinaceous components, choice of optimum solvent also depends on the respective hazard potential of the same. For the present analysis, four commonly used hazard indices were used to evaluate the overall hazard rating of a specific solvent. The chosen hazard indices are described sequentially.

(i) Vapor hazard ratio (VHR) : VHR has been considered as hazard index-1 (HI₁) for the present analysis. For a pure solvent VHR is defined as³¹ :

$$\text{VHR (} = \text{HI}_1) = \frac{\frac{P^{\text{sat}}}{P_{\text{atm}}} \times 10^6}{\text{OEL}} \quad (1)$$

where P^{sat} and P_{atm} are saturation and atmospheric pressures respectively. OEL is 8 h occupational exposure limit. VHR is recommended for its simplicity of definition and it is applicable for pure as well mixed solvent systems.

(ii) Air index (ψ_i^{air}) : A hazard rating, which accounts for environmental, ecotoxicological and occupational risk parameters³² is defined as

$$\psi_i^{\text{air}} = \frac{P_i^{\text{sat}} \times \psi_i^{\text{env}}}{P} \quad (2)$$

where P_i^{sat} is the saturation pressure of the solvent, P is the pressure of the extraction vessel and ψ_i^{env} is referred as environmental index. ψ_i^{env} can be calculated using waste reduction algorithm (WAR)³³ and it is a weighted sum of eight normalized impact scores (ψ̄_{ij}), which includes human toxicity potential, acidification potential etc. Accordingly

$$\psi_i^{\text{env}} = \sum_{j=1}^8 \alpha_j \bar{\psi}_{ij} \quad (3)$$

where α_j is the weighing factor assigned to impact factor assigned to impact category j. For the present study air index was selected as HI₂.

(iii) Indiana Relative Chemical Hazard Score (IRCHS) : It is also known as Purdue score³⁴ and incorporates the impact of a pollutant on environment as well as on works. IRCHS, selected as HI₃ of the present analysis, is a score between 0 and 100. IRCHS is defined as

$$\text{IRCHS} = \frac{(H_{\text{env}} + H_{\text{wrk}})}{2} \quad (4)$$

H_{env} and H_{wrk} represents the normalized (0–100) hazard values on environment and workers respectively. The environmental hazard value of eq. (4) includes the respective impact of the pollutant on air, water, land and ozone layer. Alternatively, H_{wrk} accounts for worker's health, exposure and safety hazard values.

(iv) Final Hazard Score (FHS) : Toxic Use Reduction Institute (TURI), at the University of Massachusetts, Lowell, developed the rating of FHS. FHS incorporates sixty-one different hazard criteria, distributed into eleven categories like physical, aquatic, bioaccumulation, disposal, chemical, atmospheric hazards, in addition to exposure potential, product hazard etc. Finally, FHS may be calculated upon adding the scores of all the categories (S_i). Therefore,

$$\text{FHS} = \sum_{i=1}^{11} S_i \quad (5)$$

FHS was considered as HI₄ for the present study.

Based on the selected hazard indices, {HI_i}_{i=1,4}, the overall hazard index (OHI) of a pure solvent was

empirically fixed as

$$\text{OHI} = \prod_{i=1}^4 \text{HI}_i \quad (6)$$

As the OHI was chosen to be a sequential product of standard hazard indices, it is expected to universally quantify the hazard potential of a pure solvent. For the mixed solvent system, the effective hazard index (EHI) was evaluated as a volume fraction (x_i) weighted average, defined as

$$\text{EHI} = \sum_{i=1}^N X_i \times \text{OHI}_i \quad (7)$$

where i represents the pure solvent index and N is the number of solvents used.

Cost estimation :

Costs of the three mixed solvent systems, namely CM, HI, EDE, were calculated based on the current unit price and the respective amount to be used in order to process a fixed amount of biomass. For example, according to the protocol of Hara and Radin²², 18 ml of 3 : 2 (volume ratio) hexane and isopropanol is required to process 1 gm of biomass. The current Indian retail price (in Indian National Rupee, INR) of hexane and isopropanol are 1.78 and 0.78 INR ml⁻¹ respectively (SRL e-catalogue, 2015-16). Therefore, the cost of solvent per gm of biomass becomes $(0.6 \times 1.78 + 0.4 \times 0.78)$ INR ml⁻¹ \times 18 ml = 24.84 INR. Similar to HI, costs of CM and EDE were also determined following the same method.

Formulating the objective function for mixed solvent optimization :

In order to select the optimum mixed solvent system, out of CM, HI and EDE, a simple objective function (y) of the following form

$$y = \frac{\prod_{i=1}^N (X_i^{\alpha_i})}{\prod_{j=1}^M (Y_j^{\beta_j})} \quad (8)$$

has been defined, where $\{X_i\}$ represents the set of favorable parameters (like TAS value, anti-inflammatory activity, overall yield of the respective extract) and $\{Y_j\}$ be the set of unfavorable parameters

(like cost and effective hazard index of the solvent) of a specific mixed-solvent system. $\{\alpha_i\}$ and $\{\beta_j\}$ are parameter specific exponents, which are purely empirical. In order to attach equal weightage to all the property quantifying parameters, $\{X_i\}$ and $\{Y_j\}$, respective α_i and β_j values were fixed at unity. It may be noted that the definitions of $\{X_i\}$ and $\{Y_j\}$ are totally dependent on the type and measurement of the specific quality. As mentioned, antioxidant property, anti-inflammatory activity and overall yield of an extract were chosen as favorable parameters, whereas cost and EHI of the corresponding mixed solvent system were selected as unfavorable parameters in the present study.

For antioxidant property, the parameter (X_1) was defined as

$$X_1 = \frac{\text{TAS value of a specific extract at an extract concentration of } 50 \text{ mg ml}^{-1}}{\text{Max TAS value out of three different extracts at the same extract concentration}} \quad (9)$$

Accordingly, X_1 becomes a normalized favorable parameter between 0 and 1. Similarly, the yield parameter X_2 has been defined as

$$X_2 = \frac{\text{Yield of extract for a specific mixed-solvent for } 500 \text{ g of biomass}}{\text{Max yield out of three different mixed-solvents under the same condition}} \quad (10)$$

The anti-inflammatory parameter (X_3) was defined with respect to the NO concentration levels in control, untreated and treated (with three extracts individually) samples of primary macrophage culture. Therefore, an intermediate quantifier (X_3'), defined as follows, was needed.

$$X_3' = \frac{[\text{NO}]_{\text{untreated}} - [\text{NO}]_{\text{treated}}}{[\text{NO}]_{\text{untreated}} - [\text{NO}]_{\text{control}}} \quad (11)$$

The final parameter X_3 , to be used in determining the objective function, was defined in relation to the normalized X_3' with respect to the corresponding maxi-

imum value as

$$X_3 = \frac{X'_3 \text{ value of an extract for a specific mixed-solvent}}{\text{Max } X'_3 \text{ value as obtained from the extracts of different mixed-solvents}} \quad (12)$$

Regarding the unfavorable parameters, $\{Y_j\}$, the parameter based on solvent cost was defined as

$$Y_1 = \frac{\text{Cost of a specific mixed-solvent (in INR g}^{-1} \text{ of biomass) for extraction}}{\text{Max solvent cost (in INR g}^{-1} \text{ of biomass) considering different mixed-solvents}} \quad (13)$$

Similar to Y_1 , the effective hazard index based unfavorable parameter (Y_2) was defined as

$$Y_2 = \frac{\text{EHI value a specific mixed-solvent}}{\text{Max EHI value, as obtained from different mixed-solvents}} \quad (14)$$

The final form of the objective function in accordance with the definitions of different normalized optimization parameters (X_i and Y_j) becomes

$$y = \frac{\prod_{i=1}^3 X_i}{\prod_{j=1}^M Y_j} \quad (15)$$

Therefore, the optimum mixed-solvent system to be used in extraction of therapeutic components from LM must be the specific one, which leads to the largest y value.

Results and discussion

Moisture content and drying curve of LM (for edible portion) :

The batch-drying curve of LM, under constant drying condition with nearly ‘bone dry’ air is shown in Fig. 1. According to the standard notion, the curve is depicted in terms of X ($=$ kg of moisture/kg of dry LM) vs t (batch time in min) profile. The initial moisture fraction (X_i) was determined to be 3.27, which is equivalent to moisture weight fraction of 0.76. The

Fig. 1. Variation of the moisture content (X , in dry basis) with drying time for the edible part of LM biomass. Insert showing the variation of $-dX/dt$ with X .

result is exactly consistent with the commonly observed moisture content range of 74.6 to 85.9% for the entire mollusk family³⁵. After the short ‘initial adjustment period’ (~ 5 min), the moisture fraction was noted to decrease almost linearly and the trend was continued up to 75 min of batch time. This portion of X vs t profile corresponds to the ‘constant rate drying’ period, marked by the flat horizontal segment of the insert plot ($-\frac{dx}{dt}$ vs X plot). As the drying area of the LM sample, similar to any biomass, is practically impossible to determine because of uneven surface morphology and expected volume shrinkage over the entire drying period, instead of actual drying rate ($N = -\frac{W}{A} \frac{dx}{dt}$) (W : mass of the dry solid and A : drying area), $-\frac{dx}{dt}$ vs X profile has been evaluated, as shown in the insert. The ‘critical moisture content’ of LM was determined to be $X_C = 1.05$. Therefore, the constant rate drying may be inferred to continue from $X_i = 3.27$ to $X_C = 1.05$. At the end of this period, dry patches are expected to appear on the sample surface. The portion of $-\frac{dx}{dt}$ vs X profile, from $X_C = 1.05$ to $X = 0$ ($=X^*$, the equilibrium moisture for ‘bone dry’ air) was found to be nearly linear, which indicates unsaturated surface drying. The well known

'second falling rate period', where the internal diffusion of the moisture essentially controls the rate of drying, was not recorded in case of LM.

Physico-chemical properties of three extracts and olive oil :

Standard physico-chemical properties :

Standard physico-chemical properties of the three extracts, along with those of commercially available, refined olive oil are summarized in Table 1. Table 1 also includes the yields of the three extracts obtained from a fixed biomass feedstock of 500 gm each. The results indicate highest yield (=12.37 gm) in case of hexane-isopropanol (HI) solvent system, whereas the yield for chloroform-methanol (CM) was the lowest (=4.32 gm). Specific gravity and refractive index values of all the extracts are similar compared to olive oil. This alternatively indicates the purity of the extracted sample⁸. However, acid values, saponification indices and iodine values of the extract samples exhibited significant variation.

Acid values of extracts were observed to be 4 to 8 folds higher than that of olive oil. Therefore, higher amount of fatty acids are confirmed to be present in all the extract samples. Moreover, a difference higher than 5 ml of KOH gm⁻¹ of sample signifies appreciable changes of fatty acid composition in LME-2 relative to LME-3.

Saponification index is a well known marker of average fatty acid chain length in fat/lipid samples, which is also related to organoleptic properties like taste, flavor etc. Remarkably high saponification indices were exhibited by LME-2 and LME-2 (304.95 and 292.74 ml of HCl gm⁻¹ of extracts respectively).

Even for LME-1, the corresponding index value was 42% higher than that of olive oil. This observation clearly reveals higher mass fraction of short-chain fatty acids in all extracts.

Though not as pronounced as acid value or saponification index, iodine values of extract samples also showed appreciable difference relative to olive oil. It is well known that iodine value is often used to determine the degree of unsaturation in constituent fatty acids of a lipid sample. Additionally, iodine value is also influenced by the position of the double bond (s) in relation to the -COOH group, which is extremely important in terms of therapeutic/nutritive value. Minimum and maximum positive differences of 5.13 and 13.18 ml of Na₂S₂O₃ gm⁻¹ of sample were observed relative to olive oil, in case of LME-1 and LME-3 respectively. The difference was as high as 10.13 for LME-2, in the same scale of measurement.

Carotene, cholesterol and triglyceride concentrations :

Total carotene, cholesterol and triglyceride contents of the LMEs and olive oil are listed in Table 2. Significantly, the total carotene of all the three extracts were found to be 70 to 133 times higher than olive oil. It may also be noted that the mussels are unable to synthesize carotene, but it originates as a component of mollusk's algal food³⁶. Carotenes are generally stored in mussel body tissues and because of their lipid-soluble nature; they are extracted with the oil. Additionally, due to its high antioxidant properties, carotene prevents the *in vivo* oxidation of lipids.

Table 1. Extract yield and standard physico-chemical properties of LME-1, 2 and 3

Yield and physico-chemical characteristics	LME-1	LME-2	LME-3	Olive oil
Extract yield (gm per 500 gm of biomass feedstock)	4.32	12.37	8.06	NA
Specific gravity (20 °C/20 °C, gm ml ⁻¹)	1.12	1.09	1.19	0.94
Refractive Index (at 32 °C)	1.50	1.49	1.51	1.47
Acid value (ml of KOH gm ⁻¹)	15.36	17.15	8.45	2.13
Saponification index (ml of HCl gm ⁻¹)	268.31	304.95	292.74	189
Iodine value (ml of Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ gm ⁻¹)	67.13	72.13	75.18	62

Table 2. Total carotene, cholesterol and triglyceride content of LME-1, 2 and 3

Extract	Carotene content ($\mu\text{gm gm}^{-1}$)	Cholesterol ($\text{gm. } 100 \text{ gm}^{-1}$ of extract)	Triglyceride ($\text{gm. } 100 \text{ gm}^{-1}$ of extract)
LME-1	660.68	12.36	23.72
LME-2	1242.43	29.36	49.26
LME-3	1043.68	16.84	22.18
Olive oil	9.34	BDL	97.38

BDL : Below detection limit.

Cholesterol concentrations of all the extracts were found to be significantly higher than olive oil. The maximum amount ($=29.36 \text{ gm. } 100 \text{ gm}^{-1}$ of extract) was detected in LME-2, whereas, the minimum was observed in case of LME-1 ($12.36 \text{ gm. } 100 \text{ gm}^{-1}$ of extract). Evidently, in olive oil, because of its plant origin, the cholesterol content was found to be below the detection limit. Though the word “cholesterol” is always related to the enhanced risk factor of cardiovascular diseases, however, cholesterol is a fundamental constituent of animal plasma membrane and serves as a precursor of bile acids, steroids and vitamin D.

Instead of high cholesterol concentration, the triglyceride content of all the mussel extracts was found to be much lower than olive oil. Mussel extracts are also reported to have lower triglyceride compared to standard therapeutic fish oils³⁷.

UV-Vis absorption spectra :

UV-Vis absorption spectra of LME-1, 2, 3 compared to olive oil are shown in Fig. 2. As mentioned earlier, all the samples were diluted in n-hexane (1 : 2 v/v). Three extracts showed significant bands at $\lambda = 671$ and 412 nm , which are attributed to $(\text{CH}_3)\text{-NO}$ and $\text{trans-C}_6\text{H}_5\text{-(CH=CH)}_n\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5\text{-}$ poly-enes and carboxylic organic compounds respectively. However, in LME-2, presence of a significant chromophore, α -tocopherol (vitamin E) was recorded according to its characteristic peak at $\lambda = 281 \text{ nm}$ under diluted condition with n-hexane⁸. No such peaks were recorded in case of other extracts as well as in olive oil. Another very prominent peak at $\lambda = 271 \text{ nm}$ was recorded, once again in spectral profile of LME-2. This

Fig. 2. UV-Vis spectra of LME-1, 2 and 3 compared to olive oil.

peak corresponds to the poly-enes/sterol derivatives present in the extract sample. No such peak was detected in case of LME-2 and 3, but clear shoulders were observed in both of the samples. This is exactly consistent with the order of cholesterol contents evaluated in the extract samples. Table 2 clearly indicates that the cholesterol concentration of LME-2 is nearly two-fold higher than that of LME-1 and 3. Therefore, the characteristic sterol peak for LME-2 must be prominent relative compared to other samples.

FTIR spectra :

FTIR spectra analysis regarding the detection of respective functional groups is summarized in Table 3. The spectra between the ranges of $3500\text{--}3000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ showed almost no peak for all the samples except for a broad peak in case of LME-2. This may be attributed either to the aqueous remnants in the sample or to the presence of associated hydroxyl groups. In the range, between $2500\text{--}1500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, all the three extracts showed similar pattern of spectral profile. At

Table 3. Functional group analysis of LME-1, 2, 3 and olive oil according to FTIR spectra

Range of frequency (cm ⁻¹)	LME-1		LME-2		LME-3		Olive oil	
	Frequency (cm ⁻¹)	Functional groups/bonds	Frequency (cm ⁻¹)	Functional groups/bonds	Frequency (cm ⁻¹)	Functional groups/bonds	Frequency (cm ⁻¹)	Functional groups/bonds
4000–3000	–	–	3285.67	C-OH (associated OH; hydrogen bonded)	–	–	–	–
3000–2500	2920.87 } 2851.40 }	-CH ₂	3011.00 } 2851.13 }	C-H stretching (<i>trans</i>) CH ₂	3011.79 } 2922.17 } 2852.35 }	C-H stretching (<i>trans</i>) CH ₂	3005.25 } 2922.01 } 2852.67 }	Cyclopropane CH ₂
2500–1500	1742.13 } 1465.90 } 1377.49 } 1063.27 } 970.38 } 825.09 } 752.99 }	Anhydrides -CH ₂ -CH ₃ Anhydrides Sulphonates Sulphates	1742.15 } 1377.53 }	Anhydrides -CH ₃ (symmetrical CH bending)	1742.55 } 1161.05 } 1066.25 } 1465.53 } 749.44 }	Anhydrides Sulphates Anhydrides -CH ₂ C=C (aromatic)	1743.18 } 1465.21 } 1377.40 } 1214.28 } 1160.78 } 1095.73 }	Saturated ester -CH ₂ Sulphates Free acids Sulphates Phosphates
1500–500	667.95 } 721.45 }	Sulphonates CH ₂	1056.71 } 824.88 } 720.81 }	-C-OH Alkyl peroxide -CH ₂			724.19 } 667.93 }	Sulphonates

1742 cm⁻¹, characteristic C=O bond stretching frequency, the common peak, except in case of olive oil, clearly indicates the presence of organic anhydrides. The most significant portion of the spectra, for all the samples, was detected in the range between 1500–500 cm⁻¹, with maximum number of peaks that indicates a broad range of structural variations. All the groups showed the presence of methylene group and once again, the presence of organic anhydride was observed in this range for all the samples except LME-2. On the contrary, LME-2 was recorded to contain alkyl peroxides in its structure that was not found in any other sample. Additionally, the IR profile of LME-1 and 3 have indicated the presence of sulphates and sulphonates. LME-3 spectrum had peaks for aromatic C=C, whereas none of the samples, other than olive oil showed the presence of phosphates and free acids in them.

Fatty acid composition analysis by gas chromatography :

The gas-chromatographic analysis of the extract

samples along with olive oil indicates the distribution of different fatty acids (FAs). Relative proportions of FAs in four different samples are depicted in Table 4. Wide distributions of FAs, from C-6 to C-24 were noted in three extract samples with varied proportions. Saturated FAs, which primarily include palmitic acid (16 : 0), stearic acid (18 : 0) and arachidic acid (20 : 0), account for 35.22% (LME-3) to 45.14% (LME-1) of the total FA content. Mean ratio of unsaturated to saturated FAs was about 1.5 (in the range of 1.21 to 1.84), which is somewhat less compared to marine mussel extracts³⁸. On the other hand, the percentage contributions of monounsaturated fatty acids (MUFAs) were observed to be nearly invariant of the extract type (21% to 23%). However, marked variation was noted in case of polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs). PUFA content was evaluated to vary from 31.7% in LME-1 to 43.8% in LME-3. Regarding n-3 and n-6 FAs, the results indicate significantly higher n-3 relative to its n-6 counterpart. For example, in LME-3, n-3 FAs contribution was about 21.73%, whereas for n-6, the same was only about 14%. In

Table 4. Relative proportions of fatty acids (wt% of total fatty acid) in LME-1, 2, 3 and olive oil

Fatty acid	LME-1	LME-2	LME-3	Olive oil
6 : 0, Caproic acid	0.22	–	0.13	–
8 : 0, Caprylic acid	0.14	–	0.1	–
12 : 0, Lauric acid	–	–	0.39	–
14 : 0, Myristic acid	2.57	–	1.55	–
16 : 0, Palmitic acid	29.45	21.75	23.81	10.34
16 : 1 n-7, Pamitoleic acid	4.32	4.22	3.82	–
17 : 0, Heptadecanoic acid	2.41	0.50	2.23	–
18 : 0, Stearic acid	4.82	5.41	1.19	1.28
18 : 1 n-9, Oleic acid	16.77	12.52	13.82	79.33
18 : 2 n-6, Linoleic acid	12.85	13.94	14.87	8.42
18 : 3 n-3, α -Linolenic acid	11.63	13.22	11.78	0.53
18 : 4 n-3, Steridonic acid	2.84	3.61	3.23	–
20 : 0, Arachidic acid	5.53	7.89	6.03	–
20 : 4 n-4, Arachidonic acid	1.81	3.36	2.06	–
20 : 5 n-3, EPA	2.57	4.27	3.39	–
22 : 6 n-3, DHA	2.07	4.24	3.33	–
24 : 0, Lignoceric acid	–	2.57	2.02	–
24 : 1 n-9, Nervonic acid	–	2.15	2.25	–

addition to the individual amount, the ratio of n-6 to n-3 FAs was recorded to vary from 0.55 to 0.68. Relevant literature indicates that in the Paleolithic period, when human's genetic profile was evolving, there was a clear balance between n-6 and n-3 FA intake³⁹. The ratio of n-6 to n-3 over the time span was predicted to be close to unity. In today's diet, the global average n-6 to n-3 ratio varies between 10 : 1 to 15 : 1⁴⁰. In general, a lower n-6 to n-3 FA ratio is highly effective in reducing the risk of several chronic diseases, which includes cardiovascular complications, cancer, inflammatory and autoimmune diseases. Therefore, the present extracts may be inferred to serve as a highly effective functional food because of its low (<1) n-6 to n-3 ratio as well as high n-3 FA content (nearly one-fourth of the total FAs).

Toxicity analysis :

The toxicity study showed that all the four doses of extracts chosen were non-toxic with merely above 98% cell viability rate in each case. Based on this observation, 10 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ was selected as the optimum dose for further bioactive studies.

Bioactivity and therapeutic potential :

Total antioxidant status (TAS) :

Variation of the total antioxidant status (TAS, in mM trolox equivalent) with extract concentration, in the range of 10–100 mg ml^{-1} , for all the three extract samples is shown in Fig. 3. All the TAS profiles are

Fig. 3. Variation of Total Antioxidant Status (TAS) for the three extracts over the concentration range of 10 to 100 mg ml^{-1} .

closely linear, with R^2 varying from 0.95 to 0.98. Evidently, the profiles are monotonically increasing functions of extract concentration, with profile slopes varying from 0.01 to 0.06 mM trolox equivalent. (mg of extract. ml⁻¹)⁻¹. Significantly, the profiles of LME-2 and 3 are nearly parallel over the stipulated concentration range (average slope of 0.015). However, for LME-1, the profile slope was observed to be as high as 0.06 mM trolox. (mg of extract. ml⁻¹)⁻¹. This indicates a progressively higher antioxidant enhancement rate at elevated concentration, which may be effective in clinical practice. As all the profiles are linear and non-intersecting, same order of antioxidant status i.e. LME-1 > LME-2 > LME-3, is being retained over the entire concentration range, within the scope of the present study. At an extract concentration of 50 mg ml⁻¹, the TAS values of LME-1, 2 and 3 were found to be 3.26, 1.59 and 0.61 (in mM trolox equivalent scale) respectively. Accordingly, the parameter, X_1 , to be used in the respective solvent optimization becomes 1.00, 0.49 and 0.19 for LME-1, LME-2 and LME-3 respectively.

Anti-inflammatory activities of extracts :

Lipopolysaccharide (LPS), a membrane constituent of Gram-negative bacteria, is known to induce local inflammation, antibody production and septic shock. On the other hand, M1 macrophage generates NO, upon metabolizing arginine, in immune response towards pathogen, like LPS. Therefore, elevated level of NO concentration is regarded as a direct marker of inflammation⁴¹.

Fig. 4 represents the NO concentration levels, after 18 h of LPS activation in untreated, DMSO (vehicle used for extract treatment), LME-1, 2 and 3 treated macrophage cell culture, along with the normal control cells. Significant increase of [NO] was recorded in untreated and DMSO treated groups compared to the normal control. A closer investigation reveals nearly 115% enhancement of [NO] upon 18 h of LPS activation. DMSO treatment has practically no effect on NO production and accumulation rates.

Fig. 4. Nitric oxide production levels from different LPS induced activated macrophage cell culture.

However, the concentration levels were observed to suppress in all the extract treated cultures. For example, [NO] was reduced from 9.3 μM in untreated group to 4.7 μM in LME-1 treated group. The bar diagram (Fig. 4) clearly indicates maximum reduction of [NO] in case of LME-2 treated group (=53%), whereas the corresponding minimum, though close to the maximum, was recorded for LME-3 treated cell culture. The intermediate optimization parameter, X_3' , as defined in eq. (11), was calculated for all the extracts. The values were found to be 0.93, 1.00 and 0.89 for LME-1, 2 and 3 respectively. As the maximum X_3' value was evaluated to be unity, the final optimization parameter (X_3) remained unchanged in relation to X_3' .

Cost analysis :

The solvent costs for three different mixed solvents were calculated based on the volume fraction weighted retail prices of solvents required to treat 1 gm of LM biomass. Following the sample calculation, demonstrated earlier, the respective solvent costs for CM, HI and EDE are 12.28, 24.84 and 6.4 INR (gm of LM biomass)⁻¹. Among the different components used in the present study, cost of hexane was

recorded to be maximum [=890 INR (gm of LM biomass)⁻¹] and that of methanol is minimum [=260 INR (gm of LM biomass)⁻¹]. Chloroform, ethanol, diethyl ether and isopropanol are in the intermediate range. On the other hand, 20, 18 and 10 ml of 1 : 2 CM, 3 : 2 HI and 3 : 1 EDE (all in v/v) respectively are required to process 1 gm of LM biomass according to the standard protocols, described earlier.

Finally, the unfavorable, dimensionless optimization parameter, related to the normalized solvent cost (Y_1), were calculated to be 0.49 for CM, 1.00 for HI and 0.26 for EDE.

Hazard rating analysis of the three mixed solvent systems :

Individual and the overall hazard indices of the three mixed solvent-systems, namely chloroform-methanol (CM, 1 : 2 v/v), hexane-isopropanol (HI, 3 : 2 v/v), and ethanol-diethyl ether (EDE, 3 : 1 v/v), were evaluated following to the methods outlined earlier. The results are summarized in Table 5. According to the standard environmental rating of commonly used organic solvents (like VHR, air index, IRCHS and FHS), chloroform has been reported to be one of the most hazardous solvent, just after CCl₄, C₆H₆ and CS₂ (Debia *et al.*, 2011). Simultaneously, its conjugate solvent, methanol, has also a moderately high rank in different hazard rating scales. For example, its VHR rank is 47, air index based rank is 52, IRCHS ranking is 47 and FHS rank is 53 out of 67 standard

organic solvents. Ethanol, on the other hand, is regarded to be one of the safest solvent, though it is conjugated with hazardous diethyl ether. Hazard ratings of isopropanol are intermediate between ethanol and methanol. In general, regarding the polar members of the chosen mixed solvents, the hazard potential based sequence is methanol > isopropanol > ethanol, whereas for the non-polar members, the respective sequence is chloroform > diethyl ether > hexane. However, it is to be noted that OHI value of chloroform is 33 and 82 times higher compared to diethyl ether and hexane respectively. Consequently, the effective hazard index (EHI), which is the volume fraction weighted average of OHIs in a mixed-solvent system, of CM was calculated to be 44 and 45 times higher relative to that of HI and EDE. Therefore, the corresponding unfavorable optimization parameter, Y_2 (defined in eq. (13)), became negligibly small for HI and EDE (=0.02) relative to CM (=1.0).

Solvent optimization :

Distributions of favorable and unfavorable parameters (X_i and Y_j), which include, anti-oxidant property (X_1), extract yield (X_2), anti-inflammatory property (X_3), solvent cost (Y_1) and solvent's hazard rating (Y_2), for three different mixed-solvent systems of the present study is shown in Fig. 5(a). Fig. 5(b) represents the variation of the corresponding objective function (y). The figure clearly indicates hexane-

Table 5. Hazard indices of different pure and mixed solvents along with the respective optimization parameter (Y_1)

Solvent	VHR	Air India	IRCHS	FHS	OHI =	Mixed Solvent	
	(HI ₁)	(HI ₂)	(HI ₃)	(HI ₄)	$\prod_{i=1}^4 HI_i$	$EHI = \sum_{i=1}^2 x_i \cdot OHI_i$	Y_2
Chloroform	25900	2.932	30.0	45	10, 2447, 450	} CM : 3, 3909, 307	1.00
Methanol	835	0.214	22.1	39	154, 013		
Hexane	4030	0.334	23.1	40	1243, 722		
Isopropanol	299	0.076	12.6	29	8, 303	} HI : 749, 554	0.02
Ethanol	78	0.106	11.1	27	2, 478		
Diethyl ether	1770	3.124	19.9	22	3037, 631	} EDE : 761, 266	0.02

Fig. 5. (a) Distributions of different favorable and unfavorable optimization parameters for the three extracts. (b) Variation of the objective function.

isopropanol to be the optimum solvent system in extraction of bioactive and therapeutic components from LM. The objective function attains a maximum value of 24.5 in case of HI, whereas for EDE and CM, the values are 21.14 and 0.66 respectively. Surprisingly, the most commonly used mixed-solvent of chloroform and methanol in extraction of lipid and lipid-soluble proteinaceous components from different biomass samples was evaluated to be the worst solvent system in the present study. The primary reason is abnormally high hazard ratings of both the components according to all the standard hazard evaluation protocols. However, if the hazard rating parameter (Y_2) is excluded from the present objective function, CM becomes the optimum solvent with an unchanged objective function value of 0.66, followed by HI (=0.49) and EDE (=0.42). This is because CM was observed to produce an extract (LME-1) resulting highest anti-oxidant parameter (X_1) and moderately high anti-inflammatory parameter (X_3). HI, on the other hand, was evaluated to produce an extract (LME-2) with highest X_3 and maximum extract yield (X_2). Though the cost of HI (respective unfavorable pa-

rameter : Y_1) was calculated to be the maximum, but it's hazard rating is negligibly small compared to CM.

It is to be noted that only five optimization parameters were chosen to sort out the optimum solvent system for the present biomass. Additional parameters, like acid value, saponification index, iodine number, carotene content and many others may be included. However, these parameters are related to indirect measurement and may be independent of the extract's therapeutic potential. Additionally, the n-3 to n-6 ratio is still a highly debated topic and a precise one to one correspondence between the ratio and related bioactivity is still not fully understood. Therefore, the present objective function was formulated to include only the direct measurement based therapeutic potentials of the extract along with the yield, cost and hazard rating of the respective solvent system.

Conclusion

The present work primarily deals with the selection of the optimum mixed-solvent, out of most commonly used chloroform-methanol, hexane-isopropanol and ethanol-diethyl ether in extraction of bioactive

and therapeutic lipids along with lipid soluble proteinaceous components from the edible part of Indian fresh water mussel, *Lamellidens marginalis*. Additionally, the three extracts obtained by using three different mixed-solvents were characterized in terms of standard physico-chemical properties, like acid value, saponification index, iodine value, UV-Vis spectra, IR spectra, cholesterol and triglyceride content, gas chromatographic analysis etc. In order to choose the optimum solvent system, a simple and easily workable objective function was formulated incorporating the extract yield, anti-oxidant property, anti-inflammatory property, solvent cost and the respective hazard rating. Negating the most commonly used mixed-solvent of chloroform-methanol, hexane-isopropanol was found to be the optimum solvent, primarily because of negligible small hazard rating compared to the previous. The proposed optimization technique may be viewed as a simple and novel pure quantitative approach to select the optimum solvent (applicable for pure as well as mixed solvents) in extraction of bioactive and therapeutic components from any biomass feedstock.

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